

RELIGION AND POLITICS FOR SUSTAINABLE PEACEBUILDING IN SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study explores the complex relationship between religion, politics, and peace-building in the South West Nigeria. This study is borne out of a deep concern about contradictory features of religious practices on one side, and politics of peace often deployed by political leaders and government to manage or resolve religious conflicts; and the study also examines the failure of politics of peace to foster sustainable development and peace-building in south western Nigeria. The purpose of religion seems to have been misunderstood and the implication for the whole world is devastating. The background and religious landscape of the South West Nigeria is significantly characterised by religious tolerance and interfaith relations and it is, to a good extent, contributing to peacebuilding interventions in Nigeria. However, religious ideologies, at times, engender aberrant behaviours with indisputable escalation of violation of religious boundaries and human rights. Qualitative approach including interviews with purposive sampling of six informants with good experience in both religion and politics across south western geopolitical zone and across the two major religions and document analysis for explanatory and exploratory results were employed. Findings show that both religion and politics are social instruments in the hands of actors and they engage the instruments both for the advancement or degradation of humans depending on their instincts and external influences. The study concludes that both religion and politics are complex and intertwined and veritable instruments for social engagements, therefore, it is recommended that religion as well as politics be deployed to promote sustainable peacebuilding in south western Nigeria.

Keywords: Paradox of religion, Religious practices, Politics, Sustainable peacebuilding, South western Nigeria, Sustainable development.

Introduction

The practice of religion and culture in Nigeria comes with a big prospect as well as a big conundrum! Religion, like politics is one of the most pervasive and powerful forces on earth and very core in human relationship. Religious ideas have infiltrated the Nigerian families, societies, politics and cultures, perhaps that is the reason both religion and politics are intertwined, aggressive and compromising. Religion is no longer a matter of self-interest in pursuit of higher truths and worship of the Supreme Being, rather, religion has been deeply rooted in socio-political worldviews. It is true that religion contributes to human value, at the same time, history clearly shows that religion has often been linked directly to the worst examples of human attitude and behaviour in relation to other people whether at individual or corporate levels. The sad truth is that many wars have been waged, many people killed, and many social unrests have been observed all in the name of religion, other than by any other institutional force in human history (Oyedapo,2022). It is appalling that religion is still grossly manipulated with unspeakable evil things perpetrated under its guise, especially in Nigeria.

The tragic event of September 11, 2001 cannot be easily forgotten in a hurry. It may be difficult to know with certainty what was in the hearts of the nineteen men who hijacked the four planes that changed the whole story of world that day. What motivated the key leaders among the hijackers and the al-Qaida (“the base”) network supporting them was their understanding of a particular text in the Holy Quran of Islamic faith. This incident was a clear manifestation of the paradox of Islamic faith which is presumed to preach peace but at the same time has been used to kill and destroy people and properties in some particular nations including Nigeria. It is even enigmatic to understand the handwritten letter left by ringleader Muhammad Atta justifying the behaviour as a religious worldview. It is imperative to know why the Jihad Manual publicised by Osama bin Laden and his several taped messages following the attacks on the World Trade Centre and the Pentagon were laced with religious imagery and language designed to motivate other faithful Muslims (Onapajo,2012). The meticulous planning and preparation were conducted in a wider framework with the focus to die along with his cohorts “to meet Allah”. How can you kill to meet the true Creator? What a paradox of religious practice in Nigeria!

Statement of the Problem

The social imperative of religious engineering through epistemic justice in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized (Oyedapo & Alade,2022.). Religion and politics are common denominators of conflict in many communities in Nigeria but government has not really lived up to expectation in managing or resolving religious conflicts (Obadare,2020). Several authors have written about the intersection of religion and politics while several summits and roundtables have been organised without actionable resolutions to the problem. The unhealthy romance of Nigerian politics and religion has brought Nigeria into a state of disrepute with unimaginable consequences as currently experienced (Kukah,2022). It is in the light of the observed social inadequacies that this study examines the intersection of religion and politics for sustainable peacebuilding in south western Nigeria as a vibrant geopolitical region.

Objectives of the Study

Generally, the study examines the role of religion and politics for sustainable peacebuilding in South West Nigeria and specific objectives are to:

- i. examine the human values of religion and politics to sustainable peacebuilding in South West Nigeria.
- ii. examine the principal factors causing religious and political challenges in South West Nigeria.
- iii. identify effective strategies for peacebuilding and conflict resolution in diversely religious and political contexts of south western Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What human values are there in religion and politics that could promote sustainable peacebuilding in South West, Nigeria?
2. What factors are responsible for religious and political challenges in South West Nigeria?
3. What strategic mechanisms can be effectively engaged to resolve religious and political conflicts in a diverse context of south western Nigeria?

Conception of Paradox of Religious Practices, Politics of Peace and Peacebuilding

Religion, like culture, is as old as man and it is often an inherent value with its idiosyncrasies. Religion is a worldview and a way of life possibly inherited at birth or acquired by personal volition. Religion is equally a belief in, and worship of a supreme being, with a controlling supernatural power and with the capacity to both reward and punish within a particular system of faith. As a way of life, religion has been traditionally part of humans, hardly separable. Religion portends peace, harmony, stability, cohesion, communion, and unity but when misused or abused by disgruntled humans, it is engaged as a tool for crime and criminality with grave social consequences. Religion, at times, is a contradiction of what it promises to be, thus, instead of giving people hope, it is engendering problems through violation of human rights with the use of unwholesome political mechanisms. Religion which is thought to be archetypally peaceful, genial and comforting has been hijacked by power mongers in the gab of politics and state actors now use religion as a cover for selfish reasons to the extent that religion is fused with the state thereby diminishing its values. Judaism unequivocally prophesied about Jesus, the Messiah but at the same time prohibited and killed him; Christianity proclaims separation between the altar and the throne but it is now engaged in romance with politics; and Islam asserts that it is a religion of peace, whereas it is always implicated as being at the vanguard of terrorism and war.

Peace processes imply social-cultural, economic, political, and religious mechanisms engaged for peace-making, peace-building and peace-keeping including the intrigues of politics. Politics of peace are diverse and are deployed through the use of suasion and direct controls which are often

irksome (Onapajo,2012, Oyedapo,2024). The intrigues associated with politics in Nigeria make politics of peace for solving religious conflicts doubtful and detrimental to the progress of the country and at the same time diminish the integrity of religions and political actors. As an offshoot of peace, peace-building involves all peace mechanisms deployed to resolve conflicts in non-violent ways with a view to transforming the structural conditions generating deadly conflict.

It is not fully understood why people believe in religion; however, psychologists have proposed several theories. For instance, while Freud believed that religious belief is a form of pathological wish fulfilment; other researchers have proposed that how the human brain works often predisposes people to believe. The human mind looks for patterns, purpose, and meaning, which may influence why people turn to religion to guide their belief systems. Parenting and cultural influences also play an important role since people tend to belong to the religion in which they were raised (Onapajo,2012, Akinola,2014). The human need to belong, combined with the desire for social connection also contributes to the desire to be part of someone larger than the self.

Religion, Politics, and Struggle for Justice

It has been estimated that there are more than 4,200 religions in the whole world, and about 4084 core political parties in 212 countries of the world, although seventy-five percent of the religious people follow one of the five main faiths which include Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Buddhism, and Hinduism. Religion as well as politics is not limited to the great minds of the Western world; the Eastern world has its own religious thoughts as well, including the well-known Hinduism and Buddhism (Obadare,2020). Hinduism is an action and polytheistic religion, replete with rituals – as opposed to Judaism, Christianity and Islam, which are the three main monotheistic religions. What happens in other religions are affecting Nigeria too, just as Nigeria shares in global politics.

Over 2000 years ago, the first known acts of what is now referred to as terrorism were perpetrated by a radical offshoot of the Zealots, an active Jewish religious sect in Judea during the 1st Century AD. The Zealots opposed the Roman Empire's rule through determined campaign, which involved assassination. The Zealot fighters used a primitive dagger *sica* to attack their enemies in broad daylight, especially on feast periods or in crowded marketplaces where there would be people to witness such violence so that a wider audience might know that they were angry. All their actions were carried out with utmost zeal to protect their religious thought; hence they were dubbed, "Zealots. Between 1090 and 1272, the Assassin, an Islamic movement used similar tactics in their struggle against Christian Crusaders who had invaded what is part of Syria today. This ugly religious trend has eventually aggravated to self-sacrifice and suicidal martyrdom evident in some Islamic terrorist groups like Boko Haram and Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP), among others (Oyedapo,2022; Nwobodo,2023). Whereas everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, ISWAP thinks otherwise.

Muslim leaders who clearly disassociated themselves from terrorists publicly reiterated that Islam is a religion of peace. However, Osama bin Laden and his network had strong supporters and allies, not only among Muslims in Afghanistan, but also in Pakistan, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia and

elsewhere. The problem lies in the fact that religion that is supposed to bring peace is undergirded by a radical philosophy of terrorism by some religious extremists. We should be concerned about what religion stands to offer us when thousands of Al-Qaida, Boko Haram, Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) and allied operatives are on the prowl to kill and destroy (Abdurasheed,2012, Suberu,2013). Common people are in the volatile web of political, economic, social, cultural and military dynamics suffering under the guise of religion. Religion that is supposed to facilitate freedom has been manipulated by a few fundamentalists to make religion evil. It is ironical also that Boko Haram operatives celebrated the 2021 edition of *Id-el-fitir*, Muslim festival on May 12 and 13, 2021 in the Niger state of Northern Nigeria with pomp and pageantry to the extent that foodstuff and drinks were shared to conquered villages to motivate them so that they could join their terrorist groups (Obadare,2020). In all of these, Nigerian politicians have a great lesson to learn.

It is paradoxical to kill and still celebrate without qualm, and also to still carry and recite the Holy Scriptures. Boko Haram, ISWAP and other deadly terrorists continue to release taped messages and their affiliation with al-Qaida, yet they are very ‘committed’ Muslims with a claim to enter *Janatul firdaus*, the highest level of heaven where Prophet Muhammad (SAWS) is. It is ambiguous to sow seed of murder, wanton killings and utter destruction of lives and properties and presume to enter gardens of paradise (Osayi,2016, Akinola,2017, Oyedapo,2022). If it is true that there is punishment of *Jahanam* in Islam with seven levels of Hell created as places of punishment and torment for sinners, then those who steal, kill and destroy God’s creation should be the eminent entrants and victims of this prescribed eternal judgment.

Instead of preparing people pleasantly to get to the desired eternity, religious people become vindictive and dangerous to live with here on earth. It is paradoxical that religious people still peddle their religious merchandise without recourse to the sacredness of life and human dignity. Religion is tainted with sentiment, faith and tradition, and therefore omits huge opportunities in everyday practices; to the extent that modern people have begun to be suspicious of the illusory and atavistic nature of religion which is not appealing to the dynamic modern man in a rationalized society (Imeanolue,2021, Kukah,2022).

Politics, Religion and Functional Peacebuilding

The thrust of functionalism theory engaged in this study postulates that religion, being a conservative force, has positive function for individuals and the society. It is therefore, worthwhile to consider the significance of both religion and politics in south western Nigeria. It is high time we have begun to consider and examine the human value of religion as well as the trajectory of politics. Imposition of cultural nuances on other cultures in the practice of religion makes religion unacceptable in different climes. Outright violation of human rights is a limiting factor in the practice of religion. Thus, the Marxists may be right to a large extent when they opined that ‘religion is an opium’. Religion makes people docile, asinine and illogical in some cases. Functionalism is the doctrine that what makes something a thought, a desire, or a pain depends not

on its internal constitution, but solely on its function or role it plays in the cognitive system in which it is a part.

The 1999 constitution of the federation of Nigeria (CFRN) affirms that Nigeria is a secular state. The Government of the federation or a state shall not adopt any religion as State Religion. The section clearly indicates that religion is a private personal affair of individuals and it does not affect the state in any way. Thus, the role of the state is to ensure that there is no coercion to follow any religious belief or creed and to ensure freedom of worship without fear (Section 10, CFRN).

Peace-building includes conflict management, conflict prevention, conflict resolution, conflict transformation, trauma healing, humanitarian action, transitional justice, non-violent social change, mutative justice, and any other post-conflict reconciliation. Gleanings from the definition of peacebuilding which are to transform conflict situation into non-violent and peaceful coexistence, the south western governors and religious leaders should appraise themselves in the light of functional religion, politics, and peacebuilding.

The Ambivalence of Politics towards Religion

The attitude of government towards religion is ambivalent. For instance, the recognition and the establishment of the hajj commission, Christian pilgrim's commission, national cathedral, national mosque, imam of the Aso rock, chaplain of the Aso rock is a subtle ploy to use religion as an agency for political reasons. Religion is therefore used as a demographic index required to register for national identity card, national passport, bank and drivers' license. The situation has degenerated to the extent of preferring religion as an index rather than competence in political posts and national governance (Oyedapo,2022, Nwobodo, 2023). Thus, a mix of religion and politics in the light of the growing phenomenon of religious extremism and political inconsistencies is a major challenge for sustainable development in Nigeria.

There is much distrust in Nigeria and also in south western Nigeria, especially regarding religious and political matters. Religion is used as a tool for almost everything that has to do with political posts and governance. When religion combines with politics, every citizen's emotion is arisen and both religious and political actors use the opportunity to protect their interest even if it is not for the public good. For instance, the nationwide report indicated that Christian members of the APC in all the 19 Northern states as well as the Christian association of Nigeria (CAN) denounced the Muslim-Muslim ticket for the 2023 presidential election for no other reason than religion (Kukah,2022).The political trend in Nigeria has weightier religious consequences than can be conceived now.

In Nigeria, like most parts in Africa, religion cannot be divorced from other aspects of living. Religion exists in the culture, vocation, politics and socio-economic practices of people and regulates their values, worldviews and aspirations. The three geo-political zones of Northern Nigeria do not agree to the constitutional view of secularity of the Nigerian states. In the northern Nigeria, rights to freedom of religion and expression are somehow restricted as observed in the case of the recent killing of Deborah Samuel, a 200-level student of the Shehu Shagari College of

Education. In fact, the Islamic fundamentalists had done several other extra-judicial killings of innocent citizens without meaningful penalty meted out to them (Kukah,2022, Njoku & Kolapo,2022, Oche,2024). However, Nasru-lahi-hi-fatihi society (NASFAT) an Islamic organization condemned the heinous crime and reiterated that such killing is alien to Islam. The action of Sultan of Sokoto as the head of Mushin community in Nigeria cleared other peace-loving Muslims of complicity when His eminence condemned the killing in his domain in strong terms, even in the heat of the moment.

The use of religion to spread hatred and division in the choice of aspirants for political positions is a bane of democracy and leadership in Nigeria. Speaking on the presidential candidacy of Muslim-Muslim ticket by All Progressive Congress (APC), the former Secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF), Babachir Lawal, a Christian, directed this to the APC Presidential Election, Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu that he would antagonise Christian majority in this country and that his political choice is a direct attack on them and even in his own native zone, because when it comes to politics and decisions, Nigerians take religion first (Erunke,2023,Oyedapo,2024).

The story of the life and scholarship of William Tyndale, an English scholar and biblical translator, humanist and Protestant martyr is another paradox. Tyndale, who was educated at the University of Oxford and became an instructor at the University of Cambridge, should be celebrated for his scholarship rather than martyred. Christian people demanded for Scriptures in the vernacular and Tyndale began working on a New Testament translation directly from the Greek in 1523. After Roman Catholic Church in England prevented him from translating the Bible there, he went to Germany in 1524, receiving financial support from wealthy London merchants to complete the translation to meet the yearnings of people who demand the vernacular version of the Bible (Suberu,2013,Oyedapo &Alade,2022). Thus, his New Testament translation was completed in 1525 and printed at Cologne, then in the face of intense persecution, he fled to Worms where he printed two more editions in 1525. What was done to Tyndale was a gross violation of what religion stands to promote and preserve. What a paradox of religion!

During electioneering campaigns, religious leaders use their religious platform to promote politicians hence, when such politicians fail to perform, such religious leaders would not have the audacity to challenge the erring politicians because they share same religious identity. The interdependence of religion and politics is seen in the fact that political and religious groups are largely indistinguishable because religion and nationalism are merged and the driving force revolves around economic factors. Both the church and mosque have been desecrated with obvious vices including corruption, unhealthy competition, and such other abuses of privileges. The south western social structure is an integrated system in which rulers, cleric officers, tenets of faith, law, ethics, religious rites, and state rituals are actually combined. The fusion of religion and the state makes religious leaders subservient to the rulers and consequently, religious practices are covertly politicized. Religion has been a basis of cultural identity and nationality around the world. For instance, among tribal peoples and throughout almost all of Nigeria today, the religious community and the political community are intricately intertwined. Now, in the modern totalitarian state in the

gab of democracy and with the influence of political gladiators, religious practices are fraught with several inconsistencies ranging from interpretation of Holy writs to militancy against human rights and sustainable development. It is worrisome still, that religious practices of both Christianity and Islam did not allow a reasonable space for minority communities of faith; especially the adherents of traditional religion.

Hostility to religion is a phenomenon fostered by the emergence of political totalitarianism, as in the case of Nazi Germany, a fascist and anti-clerical state. Restriction is placed on religious practices and supreme allegiance must be given to the state. This phenomenon resonates with a stern restriction placed on religion to the extent that the Nazi government, in 1941, concluded that National Socialism and Christianity are irreconcilable. This is an attitude of hostility toward religion as expressed in the political philosophy of communism. However, religion and politics can be integrated to promote sustainable peacebuilding without violating their cardinal principles since both institutions are largely social structures (Osayi,2016, Oyedapo & Alade, 2022).

Potential pitfalls and limitations of relying on religion as a force for peacebuilding include too much reliance on leadership and stereotypes. The complexities of economic disparities, which religion alone may not be able to resolve are part of the limitations of relying on religion for peacebuilding. Similarly, over-reliance on verbal advocacy without tangible peace building initiatives often lead to superficial and unsustainable peace efforts. Religion, in the contemporary world is fraught with doubts and biases, considering the dynamics of politics and other socio-economic challenges that negatively impact on religious practices in the south western Nigerian. Another peril of religious preachers is avarice, a factor which makes people to cast aspersion on religious leaders. A concrete religious reform is solicited to foster interfaith dialogue, inter-cultural communication to achieve robust community-based peace building outcomes.

Methodology

Qualitative approach is employed with the instrument of interviews and document analysis to have an exploratory result, considering the volatility of both religion and politics in exploring the importance of religion and politics for sustainable peacebuilding, and conflict resolution in South West Nigeria. Purposive sampling of six key informants with good experience in both religion and politics across south western geopolitical zone and across the two major religions (Christianity and Islam) was conducted.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Key informants include Professor Alaba Gbadamosi, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba (Ondo State); Professor Taofik Salako, Tai Solarin University Ijebuode,(Ogun state); Alhaji Dr Kehinde Olatunji (Lagos state);Engineer Kehinde Sajobi (Osun state); Alhaji chief Kareem Yerokun (Oyo state); Mr Abiodun Aderibigbe (Ekiti State). The key informants responded to the research questions in consonance with the statement of the problem.

Results of the interviews in response to the statement of the problem and research questions are thematically and respectively highlighted:

- i. The approximate answer is that religion has human values for harmonious and peaceful coexistence, except for sectarian, and extremist tendencies and corrupt politicians that have tainted religion in Nigeria and south western Nigeria in particular.
- ii. Respondents agreed that poverty and underdevelopment and the chasm between the rich and the poor are the causal factors of religious and political conflicts in south western Nigeria.
- iii. The consensus responses revolve around bad governance and lack of financial integrity of leadership both in the religious space and political space, therefore the strategy to resolve the agelong conflicts lie with the religious and political actors. Once they are forthright and put socio-economic structures in place, religious practices and politics will foster sustainable peacebuilding in south western Nigeria, and consequently in Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

This study is situated within functionalist theory which focuses on the positive effect of social institutions and explain that the significance of social institutions depends largely on their functions that they perform in the society. Within this theory, function refers to the extent to which a given activity promotes or demotes maintenance of a system and this is germane to this study. It is therefore, worthwhile to examine the functions of religion and politics in south western Nigeria. Religious identity, discrimination, poor leadership, injustice, ignorance, poverty, lack of dialogic relationship, and lack of political and citizenship education, and religious intolerance are main causes of religious and political challenges identified in south western Nigeria (Oyetero & Talabi, 2023). While religion can be a powerful force for peacebuilding, religious identities can sometimes be exclusionary, leading to an “us versus them” mentality that exacerbate conflicts as portrayed in the south west of Nigeria during the presidential electioneering processes heightened by the Muslim – Muslim ticket. Different interpretations of religious texts and teaching have often led to disagreements and conflicts, even within the same faith tradition (Akpanika, 2017, Idowu, 2023). There are complex and multifaceted principal factors responsible for engendering ethnic, political, and cultural challenge in south west Nigeria. Main causes of political and religious challenges in the south western Nigeria also include corruption, discrimination, injustice, bad leadership, and ethical violence. Religious practices actually impact on peacebuilding and conflict resolution; however, misuse of political power aggravates inequality and generates discontent among many groups, therefore, exacerbating tension and agitations among young people. Based on the findings, another principal factor for the ineffectiveness of politics of peace to resolve religious contradictions has been traced to the unhealthy romance between religion and politics in the region. Findings also highlight primordial factors as well as economic underpinnings as fundamental factors for the intricate and complex interplay between religion and politics.

Conclusion

Religion as well as politics that is predicated on indoctrination of hate, resentment, and bigotry cannot foster peace and security as depicted by the outcome of the study. It is unthinkable that many religious leaders are grossly bereft of religious ideas that could advance their faith; hence they resort to crime and criminality including ritual-killing, falsehood and totalitarian leadership instead of being servant leaders. Religious leaders who lack requisite skills in handling interpretation and explanation of their respective scriptures would definitely resort to eclectic behaviour of mixing truth with falsehood. The study equally reveals that incidences of religious perversion are traced to prophets and imams virtually in all the states of south west Nigeria. It is incontrovertible that poverty and underdevelopment is largely responsible for religious paradoxes identified. The study therefore concludes that religious practice in south western Nigeria is predicated on several factors including poverty and under-development, bad governance, religious identity, political cleavages, carpet-crossing syndrome, sub-normal scriptural interpretations, totalitarian attitude of religious leaders, and other neo-colonial underpinnings. Thus, religion has been grossly politicized and the brunt is heavy on an average Nigerian citizen.

Recommendations

With due diligence and gleanings from the findings of the study, following recommendations would bridge notable gaps identified, minimize religions paradoxes and strengthen politics of peace to transform south western Nigeria:

- Recognize the significance of religion as an unstoppable force that has infiltrated the heart of an average south westerner in Nigeria.
- Re-engineer, review, and reactivate religion to promote human value and sustainable development, rather than practiced as sheer rituals.
- Engage religion in praxis-oriented conflict management and resolution to entrench or strengthen peace building in the south western region of Nigeria.
- Harmonize religion and politics in a way that each would not violate their unique underlying principles to foster peace and security in south western Nigeria.
- Public policy on politics of peace should be transparent, equitable, conflict sensitive, and pragmatic to make governance people-friendly with a goal of transforming the south western region.

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